

METACOMPOSITES CONTAINING FERROMAGNETIC MICROWIRES

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ABSTRACT

Metamaterials have manifested peculiar characteristics that are inaccessible for natural materials. However, their fancy properties are usually realised from their structure, which does not make them a true piece of material. Substantial costs incurred from the manufacturing stage also remain to be solved. This paper proposes a remedy of ‘metacomposites’ consisting ferromagnetic microwires and a base material of glass fibres reinforced polymer composites. The microwires are arranged in the metacomposites as a parallel and an orthogonal manner, respectively. The microwave properties are investigated in the 0.9 to 17 GHz in a free-space with presence of magnetic bias up to 3000 Oe. Remarkably, a double-negative-index (DNG) metamaterial feature is revealed in the parallel metacomposite containing 3 mm spaced wires evidenced by a transmission window in the 1-7 GHz and a negative dispersion from permittivity spectrum. The effective wire diameter is proposed to address the permittivity discrepancy between theoretical and experimental values, which can be greatly influenced by wire spacing due to the dielectric contribution from wire-wire dynamic microwave interactions. In the orthogonal metacomposite containing wires of 10 mm spacing, the transmission window in the 1-6 GHz is observed at a much higher magnitude, nonetheless, with less wire amount donated compared with parallel metacomposite. This arises from the enhancement of wire interactions from the vertical wires thus pushing up the plasma frequency in favour of holding DNG features. The DNG characteristics disappear when the electrical component is set perpendicularly to glass fibres in the polymer composites due to possible bending of wires arising from hard contacts therein. All these features make the proposed microwires enabled metacomposites promising for microwave cloaking and sensing devices.

1 INTRODUCTION

Metamaterials have drawn considerable research interests in recent years due to their exotic properties such as double negative (DNG) feature. Since the first theoretical work from Pendry [1] and subsequent experimental confirmation from Smith [2], a number of studies have demonstrated that the DNG features are attainable from microwave [3] to optical regimes [4] by selecting the constituent building blocks with different macro/meso/micro-scales and arranging them in a periodical fashion. However, the artificial response of conventional metamaterials are often realised from their internal

structures rather than the intrinsic material properties, rendering the metamaterial purely a ‘structure’. Further, the manufacturing process persists at a rather high level due to the necessity to precisely fabricate and combine metamaterial units [5]. These two weaknesses hinder the development of metamaterials to have more flexible and tunable multifunctionalities in addition to the cost-effectiveness in the mass production.

Recently, ferromagnetic microwires have been studied for decades owing to their giant magnetoimpedance (GMI)/stress-impedance (GSI) effects and excellent soft magnetic properties [6]. The collective response arising between microwires and microwaves endorses that they can be built into microwave absorbers or sensors for various applications from electromagnetic interference (EMI) shielding to structural health monitoring (SHM). Ideally, an array comprised of periodical conductive wires can realise left-handed electromagnetic behaviour due to their plasmonic nature [7]. It follows that microwires would yield DNG characteristics taking into account the ferromagnetic resonance (FMR) in favour of a negative magnetic permeability. Carbonell et al have experimentally confirmed that a free standing Co-based wire array can produce a magnetic field-tunable DNG feature via the interaction with guided microwaves [8]. Liu *et al* have predicted that the metamaterial features can be obtained through an orthogonal array of ferromagnetic microwires and conductive carbon fibres [9]. Yet we believe that it is much more useful to deploy microwires alone to construct such metamaterial behaviour. Further, the exploitation on isolated microwires in pursuing metamaterial features would still be harnessed for high demanded microwave applications in that wires have limited mechanical ductility.

From multifunctional standpoint, it is natural to incorporate microwires into high-mechanical performance matrix materials and we would be able to introduce additional electromagnetic properties with the minimum perturbation to the excellent mechanical properties of the matrix. It has been elucidated in our review paper that the polymer-based composites containing microwires possess a series of advantages [10]: (i) low filler volume fraction ensures miniaturization of future sensors; (ii) polymer substrate provides mechanical constraint to wires without compromising their microwave sensing capabilities; (iii) flexible and sensitive tunability towards external stimuli (magnetic field, temperature, mechanical stress, etc.) is beneficial to developing microwire composites for sensing applications. Thus, the wire-composite can be a friendly medium to host possible DNG features in lieu of microwire arrays and we use the term ‘metacomposite’ to account for such system. By definition, the metacomposite should essentially meet two criteria: (i) The metacomposite is a “true” composite material rather than a structure; (ii) its ultimate properties are profoundly dependent on the fillers’ material properties as well as the geometrical parameters.

On the other hand, all the studies on the DNG feature based on microwires are restricted to Co-based ones. As known, Fe-based wires have distinguished domain structure from Co-based counterparts and, as a consequence, their static and dynamic electromagnetic behaviour are also distinct [6]. For example, their magnetization profile exhibits a large Barkhausen jump due to positive magnetization constant, which makes the dynamic behaviour can be modulated at rather high magnetic fields. In addition, Fe-based wires are more cost-effective and desirable for sensing devices and voltage transformers as opposed to Co-based wires.

In this article, we designed the polymer-based composites containing parallel and orthogonal arrays of microwires and studied their microwave properties. Key findings are summarised as follows. (i) The DNG characteristic is verified via the observation of transmission windows in the parallel metacomposite containing wires with spacing below 7 mm (critical spacing). (ii) ‘Effective diameter’ is introduced to remedy the discrepancy of theoretical and experimental results in the effective permittivity. (iii) The artificial transparency in the orthogonal metacomposites is noted and revealed in a higher level but less wire amount compared with the parallel metacomposites. (iv) The polymer matrices can exert a synergistic influence on the DNG features when glass fibres therein are placed along the wires direction. (v) The perpendicular wires in the orthogonal metacomposites can enhance the overall wire-wave interaction thus providing essential amount of dielectric contribution.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Composites processing

Amorphous glass-coated ferromagnetic microwires $\text{Fe}_{77}\text{Si}_{10}\text{B}_{10}\text{C}_3$ with a total diameter of $20\ \mu\text{m}$ and glass coat thickness of $3.4\ \mu\text{m}$ were fabricated by Taylor-Ulitovskiy technique and provided by TAMAG, Spain. The continuous microwires were embedded into 950 two layers of E-glass epoxy preregs in parallel to the glass fibres to form a parallel array with spacing of 3, 7 and 10 mm, respectively (Fig. 1(a)) [11]. An orthogonal microwire array was fabricated in a same way with a fixed vertical (along the glass fibre direction) spacing of 10 mm and horizontal spacing of 3 and 10 mm, respectively, as schematically shown in Fig. 1(b) [12]. Then two additional prepreg layers were laid up on top and bottom of the wire-containing preregs, giving a layup of four layers preregs totally. A bagging procedure was followed up on an aluminium tool plate in a required vacuum of 28-31 inchHg. As a final step of composite fabrication, a conventional autoclave curing cycle was adapted to yield the resultant orthogonal microwire composites with size of $500 \times 500 \times 1.25\ \text{mm}^3$. Relevant curing conditions are as follows: the preregs were heated at a rate of $2.4\ ^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ to $125\ ^\circ\text{C}$ and temperature was kept for 120 min before naturally cooling down to room temperature. The pressure was elevated to 0.62 MPa at a rate of $0.07\ \text{MPa}/\text{min}$ and remained for 270 min before decreasing at $0.07\ \text{MPa}/\text{min}$ per minute [13]. For comparison, a blank glass fibre-reinforced composite without Fe-microwires was also fabricated following the same process.

Fig. 1 Schematic view of manufacturing process of (a) parallel wire array composite with wire spacing of 3, 7, 10 mm, respectively and (b) orthogonal wire array composite with fixed wire spacing 10 mm perpendicular to glass fibre direction and different horizontal wire spacing of 3 and 10 mm, respectively.

2.2 Microwave characterization

The microwave properties were examined by free-space technique with the electrical component (E_k) along (Fig. 1) or perpendicular to the glass fibres in the polymer composites in 0.9-17 GHz. To track the magnetic field tunable properties, an additional external dc magnetic bias up to 3000 Oe was applied along the glass fibre direction. The effective permittivity was extracted via the obtained S-

parameters by an implanted computer program: Reflection/Transmission Epsilon Fast Model. Further details of this experimental setup can be found in Ref [14].

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Parallel Metacomposites

The transmission, reflection and absorption spectra of parallel wire composites under external fields up to 3k Oe are presented in Fig. 2. Notably, a transmission window is observed in the absence of external field (Fig. 2(a)), together with dips in reflection and absorption spectra corresponding to the frequency band of 1 to 7 GHz. The transmission window reveals that negative permittivity and permeability are simultaneously obtained for the concerned composite, i.e., the wires behave as transmitting structure in this condition. Unlike magnetic field-tuned double negative behaviour realized in previous studies, [15-17] this metacomposite behaviour is achieved without an external magnetic field, which is defined as the ‘natural’ metacomposite feature. This eases the application of such materials in compact devices or lightweight structures where extra magnets are considered as a burden. Meanwhile, it is worth mentioning that this metacomposite behaviour can be obtained only if the wire spacing is below a critical spacing (7 mm in the present study), which likely relates to the origin of multi-peak absorption and the modulation of plasma frequency that will be discussed later.

Fig. 2 Frequency plots of (a) transmission and (b) absorption coefficients of parallel metacomposites containing microwires of different spacing in 0.9 to 17 GHz frequency range.

From absorption spectra (Fig. 2(b)), we note that, at a lower frequency band, the distinguished absorption peak is induced by the natural ferromagnetic resonance (NFMR) of microwires. One can calculate the FMR frequency, according to

$$f_{FMR} = \gamma(M_s + H_a / 2\pi) \quad (1)$$

where γ , M_s and H_a are gyromagnetic ratio, magnetization saturation and anisotropy field, respectively [18],[19]. Substituting $M_s=828$ Gs and $\gamma/2\pi=2.8$ MHz/Oe into the equation [12], noting $H_a \ll 2\pi M_s$, we obtain $f_{FMR}=2.3$ GHz, which is close to the experimental value. The small discrepancy between the calculation and the experimental result is probably due to the non-uniformly distributed internal frozen-in stresses formed during the wire fabrication process, resulting in fluctuations of intrinsic magnetoelastic anisotropy field [20]. When the wire spacing is large (e.g., 10 mm), the resonance frequency shifts to a higher value with increasing applied field, which is in accord with Kittel's law [21].

We now turn to effective permittivity computed from the transmission/reflection coefficients obtained from the free-space measurement (Fig. 3). As is known, periodical structures constructed of conductive wires prominently dilute the electron concentration in the composites [7]. On the other hand, the polymer matrix has negligible magnetic and dielectric resonance. Therefore, the plasma frequency (f_p) of composites with ferromagnetic wires in parallel arrangement could be simplified to that of periodical conductive arrays and expressed as

$$f_p^2 = c^2 / (2\pi b^2 \ln(b/a)) \quad (2)$$

which is determined by the wire radius a and spacing b [7]. We obtain f_p of 4.8, 6.6 and 16.6 GHz for composites with wire spacing of 10, 7 and 3 mm, respectively. However, from the inset of Fig. 4(b), we notice that there is a large discrepancy between these calculated values and the experimental ones when the wire spacing is larger than 3 mm, i.e., 1.4 GHz for $b=10$ mm, 1.6 GHz for $b=7$ mm, respectively.

To understand this failure in predicting the plasma frequency, apart from the influences of topological factors in mesostructural scale, it is established that the dielectric response of ferromagnetic wires is controlled on the surface through modifying surface plasmons by creating circumferential magnetic field [7]. Thus the main dielectric response to electromagnetic waves is expected to come from the outer shell domain of wires. However, for Fe-based wires, the outer shell domain only occupies a rather trivial portion of the whole wire volume [6, 22]. From the dielectric point of view, the effective wave-matter interaction area has dramatically reduced. For convenience, we introduce herein a term of 'effective diameter', a_{eff} , to account for the equivalent interaction area. In this sense, f_p should be modified as follows.

$$f_p^2 = c^2 / (2\pi b^2 \ln(b/a_{eff})) \quad (3)$$

For $b=10$ and 7 mm, the effective diameter remains extremely small resulting in very low plasma frequency, but as b is reduced to 3 mm, there appears a marked increase of f_p , suggesting that the effective diameter is significantly compensated. It is known that the domain structure of magnetic materials and impedance tensor can be modified via the dynamic wire interactions [23]. Thus the disappearing discrepancy in f_p can be understood in that the dielectric response from long-range dipole-dipole interaction within inter-wire range provides an offset to the induced circumferential magnetic field and hence enhances outer shell domain volume [24], which is advantageous for absorption of microwave energy. Clearly, proper tailoring techniques such as current annealing to obtain wires with well-defined circumferential domain structure [6, 25] can not only make the plasma frequency of their composites more predictable, but also eliminate hard phases in the microwire so that we would eventually obtain better field-tunable properties of the microwire composites.

Fig. 3 Frequency dependencies of (a) real part and (b) imaginary part of effective permittivity of microwire composites with different wire spacing, 3, 7, and 10 mm, respectively. The inset shows the enlarged real part of effective permittivity in frequency band of 0.7–3 GHz

3.2 Orthogonal Metacomposites

One should note that the parallel wire metacomposite with 3 mm spacing has relatively high reflection due to the large wire inclusion content (*not shown here*). An orthogonal array is herein proposed to remedy this issue. The orthogonal wire metacomposites were illustrated in Fig. 1(b) and also followed a same curing protocol to that of parallel metacomposites. The transmission coefficients of composites containing microwire arrays of different configuration measured along the glass fibres in the absence of external field are shown in Fig. 4. Strikingly, a much higher transmission window is observed in the frequency range of 1-6 GHz in the 10 mm spaced orthogonal wire composite, verifying a double-negative feature. This could be explained by, on one hand, a negative permeability dispersion obtained above the FMR frequency originated from the longitudinal anisotropy field of the used Fe-based microwires [6], and, on the other hand, a negative permittivity dispersion realised by the plasmonic behaviour of horizontal wire arrays along the E_k (Fig. 1) [7,11]. Besides, it is worth mentioning that all the displayed metacomposite features are obtained without the assistance of external field, which provides more degrees of freedom in applying such materials for cloaking devices from an engineering point of view. In another perspective, for the orthogonal wire array with 3 mm spacing, the transmission is bit larger than the 3 mm parallel array composite. This improvement is logically attributed to the additional wire array perpendicular to E_k (Fig. 1(b)). For such orthogonal configuration, both permittivity and permeability are enhanced. The improved permittivity comes from the dielectric response of perpendicular wires due to some small axial component of the electric field, which also generates circumferential magnetic field that enhances the permeability to a similar extent [26]. However, the extra contribution to permeability from the excitation of magnetic component of microwave field along the additional wire array should be also considered [27]. Thus transmission of the 3 mm orthogonal microwire array composite can be eased through the improved impedance match, taken into account that:

$$Z = (\varepsilon/\mu)^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 4 Transmission coefficients of composites with parallel and orthogonal wire arrays with E_k along glass fibres in the frequency range of 0.7 to 17 GHz without external fields.

To further recognise the effect of glass fibres in the polymer composites on microwave behaviour from the matrix, we present in Fig. 5(a) the transmission coefficients of the 10 mm orthogonal microwire array composite when E_k is along and perpendicular to glass fibres, respectively. Remarkably, the transmission window disappears for the latter case. Considering the glass fibres are unidirectional, arranging microwires along the glass fibres can contribute to the DNG features through the preservation of the continuous microwire configuration. In this scenario, microwires are more likely to assign themselves into the gaps among in-prepreg and/or between-layer glass fibres, making the classic dilute plasma medium theory and assumptions on microwires of perfect ferromagnetic components still valid. On the contrary, the hard physical contact between glass fibres and vertical microwires would lead to considerable stress concentration on the wire surface (Fig. 5(b)), even the bending of the microwire after curing. When measuring perpendicularly to glass fibres, this stress can not only impact magnetic response arising from the modification of domain structure, making the NFMR characteristic hard to predict, but also possibly damage the plasmonic behaviour of continuous vertical microwires, rendering the negative permittivity impossible. Therefore, wire-orientation can profoundly impact on the observed DNG features, i.e., metamaterial characteristics can be turned on/off by simply rotating composite by 90 degrees. Note that the above on/off behaviour can be further extended to an angle-dependent metamaterial behaviour, giving the possibility of mechanically tuning the fabricated metamaterials. This indicates a possible new path for the dynamic control of electromagnetic wave's propagation in the metamaterial devices. Future work is necessary to find out the relationship between the metamaterial behaviour and the microwire-orientation angles.

Fig. 5 Frequency plots of transmission dispersion of orthogonal microwire array composite and (b) schematic view of vertical and horizontal microwires in the polymer matrices.

Fig. 6 Frequency plots of real part ε' of permittivity of the orthogonal microwire array composites. Inset is a zoomed view of part of the curve inside the square mark.

So far we have addressed the DNG characteristics and the influences from the matrix material. To look further into the underlying physics of the studied composites, we present the real part of effective permittivity of experimentally observed orthogonal array microwire composite in Fig. 6. Using Eq. (2), we have calculated earlier that the f_p of 4.8 GHz and 16.6 GHz for the parallel wire array composite with spacing of 10 mm and 3 mm, respectively. However, as indicated in the figure, the plasma frequencies are increased respectively to 6.1 GHz and over 17 GHz for the two composites. This is also consistent with the observed transmission windows associated with DNG features in the corresponding frequency band. As per a previous study, the overall dielectric response of the orthogonal composites can be enhanced via the microwave interactions between vertical wires and small axial component of E_k [11]. In other sense, we can consider the vertical wires as the short-cut dielectric components among adjacent horizontal microwire and the small amount of the increased f_p can be attributed to the extra response from these equivalent short wires. It is worth remarking that, the plasma frequency can be further increased by adding more vertical wires into the composite would elevate the f_p or performing a treatment such as stress/current annealing on the wires prior to incorporation into polymer matrices [6, 25].

4 CONCLUSION

In this article, a new kind of ‘metacomposites’ containing ferromagnetic microwires is introduced into the existing metamaterial family and manifests itself a true piece of material rather a ‘meta-structure’. The microwave properties of the metacomposites containing parallel and orthogonal wire arrays are thoroughly investigated in the frequency band of 0.7 to 19 GHz. A remarkable transmission window is noted in 1-7 GHz in the parallel metacomposite containing 3mm spaced array, suggesting a double-negative metamaterial characteristic. A term of ‘effective diameter’ is proposed to remedy the discrepancy between the theoretical values and experimental results of plasma frequency. In the orthogonal metacomposites, the transmission window is obtained at a much higher level, albeit less amount of microwires included. The role of glass fibres in the polymer composites is elucidated by arranging E_k perpendicularly and this can surprisingly suppress the observed transmission windows in addition to DNG features. All the results indicate the metacomposites are very promising for microwave sensing and cloaking applications.

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